

lungs, liver, adrenal cortex and even human milk^{4,6}. Toxicity in the olfactory mucosa and the olfactory bulb due to exposure to 2,6-dichloro-methylsulphonylbenzene (2,6-DCB) and 2,5-dichloro-methylsulphonylbenzene (2,5-DCB) were compared in mice. Female NMR1 mice were given a single i.p. injection of 2,6-DCB (16,32, and 65mg/kg BW) or 2,5-DCB (65mg/kg) and killed 14 days later. Transversal tissue sections through the entire nose were examined using light microscopy and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) in the cortex, cerebellum and the olfactory bulb was quantified using a Sandwich Elisa technique⁷.

Only 2,6-DCB induced toxicity while 2,5-DCB did not. Fourteen days after a single dose of 2,6-DCB (65mg/kg BW), severe damage was detected in the dorsal meatus of the olfactory mucosa. The Bowman's glands were completely obliterated, the basement membrane appeared irregularly thick, there was extensive fibrosis and there was a thin ciliated epithelium that replaced the neuroepithelium. The nerve bundles also appeared degenerated and the olfactory neurons eradicated. There was a significant increase of GFAP detected only in the olfactory bulb after administration of 2,6-DCB (16, 32 and 65 mg/kg BW). The results from this study show that 2,6-DCB is a potent olfactory toxicant that induces an increase of GFAP in the olfactory bulb while 2,5-DCB shows no signs of any toxicity.

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The effect of prostacyclin on the ultrastructure and on the mixed function microsomal oxygenate system in the rat liver. Toxicity studies

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Female Wistar rats were treated with prostacyclin (3x100/ug/kg i.p., daily:) for different period of time (3 days, 9 days and 70 days respectively.) After the relevant period of time the animals were killed and their liver samples were investigated electron microscopically and biochemically. The fine structure showed distinct changes without serious degenerative lesions, while the biochemical parameters showed a significant increase in the cytochrome P450 content after a short treatment, while the continuation of prostacyclin administration caused a significant and long-lasting decrease of this enzyme. The liver aniline-hydroxylase content decreased also significantly, while the aminopyrine-N-demethylase enzyme showed no change. Our final conclusion is that prostacyclin has no (serious) hepatotoxic effect.

Influence of oestrogens on formation of reactive oxygen species in liver microsomes of different aged male wistar rats

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Metabolic pathways of oestrogens are the formation of catecholestrogens (CE; 2- and 4-hydroxy-oestrogens), redox cycling of CE and free radical generation, mediated through cytochrome P450 (P450) oxidase/reductase activity. We checked the oestrogens oestradiol (E₂), oestradiol valerate (E₂V) and ethinyloestradiol (EE₂) for formation of reactive oxygen species in vitro and ex vivo in male Wistar rats in dependence on age.

In liver microsomes of 10-, 30-, 60- and 270-day-old rats the influence of E₂, E₂V and EE₂ (10⁻⁶-10⁻³ M) on NADPH-Fe⁺⁺-stimulated lipid peroxidation (LPO), H₂O₂ generation and lucigenin (luc) and luminol (lum) amplified chemiluminescence (CL) was investigated. The same parameters, additionally P450 content and monooxygenase activities were measured in liver microsomes after subchronic administration of the oestrogens (1, 10 mg/kg orally).

The most important results are the strong inhibitory capacities of the oestrogens in vitro on LPO in the order of E₂V < E₂ < EE₂, most pronounced in 10-, 60- and 270-day-old animals. In microsomes of 30-day-old rats with the highest control LPO the antioxidative effect of the oestrogens was lower. Whereas the H₂O₂ generation was not changed by E₂, enhanced by E₂V, but diminished by EE₂ in all age groups, CL luc and CL lum were inhibited in the order of E₂ < E₂V < EE₂.

Also after subchronical treatment of the rats the antioxidative action of the oestrogens was evident, microsomal LPO was inhibited in the order of E₂ < E₂V < EE₂. Only E₂V enhanced microsomal P450 content, whereas all oestrogens inhibited ethylmorphine N-demethylation. But enhanced H₂O₂ generation and increased CL luc also indicate a formation of reactive oxygen species by these oestrogens. CE (1 mg/kg orally) enhanced H₂O₂ generation and CL luc without inhibiting LPO. Obviously in vitro the antioxidative phenolic structure of the oestrogens dominates, whereas after in vivo administration the dose- and age-dependent biotransformation produces pro-oxidative in addition to antioxidative structures.

Salicylates transport into the rat brain under the influence of mono-ketocholic acid

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Acetylsalicylic acid (ASA) and lysine acetylsalicylate (LAS) transports into the rat brain through the intact blood-brain barrier (BBB) under the influence of 3-alfa,7alfa-dihydroxy12oxo-5beta-cholanate (MKH) had been examined.

Liposolubility of drugs had been determined *in vitro* measuring their solubility in water and oil fraction in the present phosphate puffer (pH = 7,4) and olive oil. ASA liposolubility was 2 % in relation to puffer and LAS liposolubility was 12 %. Anesthetized rats received 50 mg per kg ASA and 90 mg per kg LAS via the right a. axillaris to the CNS. The experimental groups were treated subcutaneously by 0,2 % sodium salt of MKH (at the dose 1 ml per kg) 30 min. before the ASA or LAS injection. Blood samples from the left jugular vein and brain samples: brainstem, cerebellum, right and left cerebral hemispheres, were taken in 60th and 150th sec. Salicylate concentrations were measured by spectrofluorometric method. The ratio between blood-brain concentrations showed that salicylate penetration from blood to brain might depend from liposolubility of injected drugs. The presence of MKH did not increase significantly transition of ASA, but affect the LAS transition through the rat BBB into the CNS, especially in 60th sec (p < 0,05).

Prediction of human drug metabolism from *in vitro* studies

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Metabolism of drugs in human has to be known very early during the development and even during the discovery phase, in order to help designing better drugs, clinical studies and predicting drug interactions. Therefore *in vitro* studies are very important to reach this goal. Most of these studies should be conducted with human material since drug metabolism is quite different between animals and men. Now tools are available for such predictions; from the more physiological to the more molecular they are: human hepatocytes, cell lines, subcellular fraction of human tissues, pure enzymes (essentially expressed in heterologous systems), antibodies and DNA probes. Some are commercial. In association, these tools now allow to predict which metabolites will be produced, the ratio of the metabolic pathways, some pharmacokinetics parameters and, drug interactions (induction as well as inhibition). A correct prediction necessitates the use of several methods and the knowledge of parameters which are not easily accessible such as hepatic concentration of the drug, hepatic concentration of the different CYP. The validity of the systems will be presented, discussed (particularly some of the limitations) and illustrated by a few examples: production of metabolites, generation of toxic metabolites, drug inhibition and induction. All those methods can be applied on small amounts of drugs, very early in development; although these methods need some refinement, they give important and reliable informations.

Effect of the extracellular matrix composition on the expression of glutathione S-transferase isoenzymes in organotypical hepatocyte cultures

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Collagen gel cultures of hepatocytes have been proposed as long-term *in vitro* models for pharmaco-toxicology. Usua-

ally in both models, collagen gel sandwich and immobilisation cultures, hydrated collagen type I, extracted from rat tails is being used as the extracellular matrix (ECM). *In vivo*, however, the ECM composition in the space of Disse is much more complex. Since xenobiotic biotransformation in hepatocyte cultures is generally thought to be dependent on several factors including soluble medium ingredients, cell-cell interactions, growth factors and the ECM composition, the expression of the phase II key enzyme, glutathione S-transferase (GST), was studied in rat hepatocytes using different culture models in which the ECM composition was adapted towards the *in vivo* situation. Organotypical hepatocyte cultures with a complex ECM consisting of mixtures of collagen type I (CI), collagen type IV (CIV, 50 ng/cm²), heparan sulphate proteoglycan (HSPG, 6 ng/cm²), fibronectin (FN, 50 ng/cm²) with and without laminin (LM, 50 ng/cm²) were compared to cultures with only CI being present. Also commercially available (Boehringer-Ingelheim) CI was compared to CI obtained in the laboratory.

GST activities were measured using 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene, 1-2-dichloro-4-nitrobenzene, 7-chloro-4-nitrobenzo-2-oxa-1,3-diazole and ethacrynic acid as a general substrate and as a substrates for the Mu, Alpha and Pi class GST isoenzymes, respectively. Albumin secretion was quantified as an additional functional parameter. It was found that after 7 days of culture the albumin secretion was higher in collagen gel sandwich than in immobilisation cultures (about 40 %). In both culture systems, however, no effect of the ECM composition on the albumin secretion could be observed.

With respect to the phase II biotransformation capacity, the same values as observed for the general, Alpha and Mu class GST activities in organotypical hepatocyte cultures with CI were found in cultures with a complex ECM. The Pi class GST activity increased as a function of culture time but that was the case in all the culture models. It reached, however, the highest values under the former culture conditions, namely when CI was prepared in the laboratory. The lowest values were seen with commercially available CI.

In comparison with the values observed in freshly isolated cells, a general trend towards a decrease of the total, and Alpha class GST activities, a maintenance of the Mu class and an increase of the Pi class GST activities was seen.

In conclusion, in organotypical collagen gel cultures of rat hepatocytes GST isoenzyme expression undergoes changes as a function of culture time. Enrichment of the ECM composition towards the *in vivo* situation, however, cannot prevent these changes.

Intestinal enzymes, P-glycoprotein and their role in drug absorption and metabolism

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Intestinal Phase I metabolism and active extrusion of absorbed drug have recently been recognized as major determinants of oral drug bioavailability. Both cytochrome P-450 3A4 (CYP3A4), the major phase I drug metabolizing enzyme in humans, and the multidrug efflux pump, MDR or P-glycoprotein (P-gp), are present at high levels in the vil-